

A MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF *RHEUM* SPECIES OF UZBEKISTAN USING DNA BARCODING

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Abstract. Identifying species according to their morphological characters, which was main criteria for species discrimination for many years, cannot now provide us with a good result. Thus, using genetic data is one of the best approaches in order to distinguish species. DNA barcoding (sequencing short, standardized regions of the genome) can be a powerful tool to identify species. In this study, we used DNA barcoding method to genetically characterize our *Rheum* species which was known as *Rheum wittrockii* from morphological identification. Two DNA barcode markers, namely ITS and *matK* were assessed to increase the accuracy and reliability of plant species identification. This multi-locus approach helped to overcome the limitations of single marker usage and provided us with a reliable result.

Keywords: molecular identification, *Rheum* genus, DNA barcoding, sequence data.

Introduction

The genus *Rheum* L. (rhubarb) contains about 60 species of perennial herbs, belonging to the *Polygonaceae* family. Rhubarbs have been known worldwide (in Asia, in particular) as medicinal and edible plants [1]. The species of genus *Rheum* occur across Asian (Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bhutan, China, India, Iran, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, Syria, Turkey) and European countries [2]. In Uzbekistan 8 species of *Rheum* (*R.cordatum*, *R.tataricum*, *R.maximowiczii*, *R.wittrockii*, *R.darvasicum*, *R.fedtschenkoi*, *R.macrocarpum* and *R.turkestanicum*) are distributed and some of them have been traditionally used in local medicine [3].

Figure 1. *Rheum wittrockii* used in this study (Bobotog, Surkhandarya, Uzbekistan).

Due to the morphologic similarity of *Rheum* species, the taxonomy of this genus highly depends on DNA barcoding, a new molecular diagnostic technology. DNA barcoding has been providing consistent and reliable results regardless of the age, plant part, or environmental factors of the sample [4,5]. Because of its high diversity and mutation rate, ITS2 has been shown in recent

research to be a promising candidate DNA barcode for the identification and classification of many different plant taxa [6,7]. ITS2 was used to identify 359 species of southern herbs from China, 96.57% of species could be successfully identified at the genus level by the BLAST method [8]. At present, DNA barcoding technology relies on chloroplast loci, and the chloroplast gene is now considered a species-level DNA barcoding [9,10]. Using the chloroplast gene as a plant, DNA barcode can prevent identification failures caused by gene deletion and low PCR amplification rate [11]. The *matK* gene sequences provided valuable information for identification of *Rheum* species of China [5]. We aimed to identify species of *Rheum* genus of Uzbekistan at the genus as well as species level via DNA barcoding.

Material and methods

Plant material

We used herbarium samples of *Rheum wittrockii* (Fig.1) collected from Bobotog, Surkhandarya region. Herbarium materials of this species were stored in the National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH).

Genomic DNA extraction

Total genomic DNA was extracted from dried leaves using DNA extraction kit (Tiangen). The concentration of DNA was measured by nanophotometer (IMPLEN, Germany). DNA samples were also visually examined by 1.0% agarose gel electrophoresis.

PCR amplification

PCR was carried out in 25 µl of reaction mixture, consisting of 12,5 µl of DreamTaq 2x PCR Master Mix (Thermo Scientific), 1 µl of each primer, nuclease free water (Invitrogen) and 1 µl of total DNA (50 ng/µl). The ITS region was amplified using ITS1 (TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG) and ITS4 (TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC) primers ([Michiel Op De Beeck](#)), and for *matK* gene amplification we used *matK*-413f-3 (TAATTTACGATCAATTCATTCAACATTTC) and *matK*-1227r-3 (GARGATCCRCRTRATAATGAAAAAGATTT) ([Jacqueline Heckenhauer, 2016](#)).

PCR amplifications were performed with Bio-Rad PCR Thermal Cycler under the following cycling conditions: for ITS, initial denaturation at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 35 cycles at 94°C for 30 s, 55°C for 45 s and 72°C for 60 s and a final extension at 72°C for 8 min, and for *matK*, initial denaturation at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 35 cycles at 94°C for 30 s, 52°C for 60 s and 72°C for 60 s and a final extension at 72°C for 8 min. PCR products were electrophoresed on 1.5 % (w/v) agarose gel in 1X TBE buffer at 120 V for 30 minutes and then gels with amplification fragments were visualized under UV light (Fig.2).

Sequencing

PCR products were cleaned using ExoSAP-IT™ PCR PRODUCT CLEANUP reagents with no sample loss by removing unused primers and nucleotides. The BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit was used for Sanger sequencing. Sequencing products were loaded onto the SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Primer areas were removed from the DNA sequences and we obtained accurate and consistent sequences using Sequencher 4.1.4.

Results and Discussion

BLAST identification results of ITS and *matK* sequences

Similarity search method (BLAST) was used to compare ITS and *matK* sequences. At genus level, both of these barcodes was *Rheum* genus, and in species level identification, *matK* sequence had the highest success rate, which was in 95,83% of similarity with *Rheum wittrockii* Lundstr. from NCBI dataset (MT918089.1; EU840484.1) (Table 1).

Table 1.

The Blast results for matK locus of database search match the similarities of studied Rheum species.

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
✓ Rheum palaestinum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum palaestio...	804	804	100%	0.0	97.29%	2461	FJ872099.1
✓ Rheum acuminatum chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum acumina...	797	797	100%	0.0	96.88%	161306	MN564922.1
✓ Rheum webbianum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum webbian...	797	797	100%	0.0	96.88%	2449	EU840465.1
✓ Rheum rhomboideum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum rhomboi...	797	797	100%	0.0	96.88%	2449	EU840462.1
✓ Rheum spiciforme chloroplast matK gene for maturase, partial cds, isolate S1	Rheum spiciforme	797	797	100%	0.0	96.88%	1271	AB115693.1
✓ Rheum racemiferum chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum racemife...	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	161682	MN564928.1
✓ Rheum rhomboideum voucher HuangXH18-01 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum rhomboi...	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	161833	NC_066819.1
✓ Rheum spiciforme voucher deng7167 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum spiciforme	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	161589	NC_066818.1
✓ Rheum racemiferum voucher ZQ19-05 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum racemife...	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	161915	NC_066816.1
✓ Rheum lhasaense chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum lhasaense	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	161820	MZ328078.1
✓ Rheum australe tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum australe	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2448	EU840477.1
✓ Rheum sp. Liu rh6265 tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum sp. Liu r...	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2448	EU840476.1
✓ Rheum tibeticum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum tibeticum	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2448	EU840475.1
✓ Rheum moorcroftianum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum moorcrof...	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2449	EU840468.1
✓ Rheum reticulatum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum reticulatum	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2449	EU840467.1
✓ Rheum spiciforme tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum spiciforme	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	2449	EU840461.1
✓ Rheum spiciforme chloroplast matK gene for maturase, partial cds, isolate S2	Rheum spiciforme	791	791	100%	0.0	96.67%	1271	AB115694.1
✓ Rheum acuminatum chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum acumina...	785	785	100%	0.0	96.46%	161655	MN514858.1
✓ Rheum uninerve voucher ZQ19-03 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum uninerve	785	785	100%	0.0	96.47%	161927	NC_066817.1
✓ Rheum przewalskyi tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum przewals...	785	785	100%	0.0	96.46%	2449	EU840463.1
✓ Rheum przewalskyi chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum przewals...	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	161740	MN564926.1
✓ Rheum pumilum voucher ZHJ18-48 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum pumilum	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	162208	MZ997430.1
✓ Rheum pumilum chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum pumilum	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	162213	NC_058530.1
✓ Rheum pumilum chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum pumilum	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	162156	MT066040.1
✓ Rheum tataricum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum tataricum	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	2449	EU840491.1
✓ Rheum pumilum tRNA-Lys (trnK) gene, partial sequence, and maturase K (matK) gene, complete cds: chloroplast	Rheum pumilum	780	780	100%	0.0	96.25%	2448	EU840473.1
✓ Rheum delavayi maturase K (matK) gene, partial cds: chloroplast	Rheum delavayi	774	774	100%	0.0	96.04%	765	MF786835.1
✓ Rheum delavayi voucher ZHJ18-31 chloroplast, complete genome	Rheum delavayi	774	774	100%	0.0	96.04%	162374	MZ997431.1

The results in Table 1. suggested that the *matK* region discriminated down the *Rheum* species to genus level.

Table 2. The results of identification of the Rheum wittrockii species with 2 locus

DNA-barcode	Consensus nucleotide sequences (bp)	Identification results in BLAST
ITS	TTGTGCGAAACCTGCGCGAGCAGACAGACCCGCGAACCCTCTCTAACCCG CCGTCGGTCGGTAGGGGGGGTGGCTCTCTTCTGAGTCCTCCCTCCCTCCC TCCCGGCGTGCGCCAACCAAAACCCCGGCGGGATTGCGCCAAGGACTATG AAACAAAAGCGCGTCCCCTGCGCCCCGGCACCCCGGCGCGCGCGGGAC GTCGTCTTTCTACCAAACAGAACACTCTCGGACGGATTTGGCTTCGATC GATGAAGAACGTAAAATGGATCTTGTGTAATTGCAAAATCCCTGATTGGCA CCAGCGCCCCGTGCCGGAAGCATCGCGTCTCGCGGGACCCCG GGCGCCAGAGGGCCCCGACCCACCCGTCGACCCAGATCAGGCGGG ACTACC	GenBank Sequence ID: KF258708.1 <i>Rheum przewalskyi</i> ITS1, ITS2 Identities: 85.81%
<i>matK</i>	TACTCTAAAAGAGATCTGTTCCGATTTTCAAAAAAAAAAATCAAAT TCTTATTGTTTCCTATATAATTCCTACGGGGAATGCAATCCATCTTCGTTT TTTCTCGCAATCAATCCTCTCTTTCGATCAACATCTTACGGAGCCTTT CTTGACGAGTTTATTCTACCTAAAGTTAGAACATTTTGTAAGTATT TACTAAGCATTATGGGGTTATCCTGTGGTCTTCAAGGACCCCTTTCTGC ATTATGTTAGATATCAGGAAAATGGATTATGGCTTCAAGGGGGCATT TTTCTGATGACTAAATTGAAATATTACTTTGTCATTTCTGGCAATATAA TTTTTCCCTGTGGTTGCAACAAGAAGAATCTATATCAATCAATCATCAA ATCGGCCACGGAGTTTATGGGTTTCTTTAAGTGTACGACTAAACCCG TCCGTGGTACGGAGTCAAATGTAA	GenBank Sequence ID: FJ872099.1 <i>Rheum palaestinum</i> maturase K (<i>matK</i>) gene Identities: 97.29%

The results of genotyping for two consensus sequences show a high level of reproducibility of the amplification results for these markers. Similarity in the BLAST database was demonstrated, with a confidence level of 95-97%.

Figure 2. Gel electrophoresis results of ITS and matK region amplification: 1. 100 bp DNA Ladder; 2. ITS; 3. ITS; 4. matK

Phylogenetic analysis based on *matK* sequences

The sequenced *matK* and other 18 *matK* sequences of *Rheum* species retrieved from NCBI were used to construct a phylogenetic tree (*Oxyria digyna* as an outgroup). Sequence alignments were done in MEGA5 (Tamura et al. 2011) using MUSCLE (Edgar 2004a, 2004b) method. ML tree was constructed using RAxML v.8.2.10 (Alexandros et al., 2014) with 1000 bootstrap replicates.

Figure 3. Phylogenetic tree of genus Rheum species constructed based on matK gene sequences (Numbers in the nodes are the bootstrap values from 1000).

The alignment analysis of *matK* region of our sample with the *matK* sequences of *Rheum wittrockii* from GeneBank showed only 4.1 % difference.

Conclusion

In this study, samples of *Rheum wittrockii* were successfully identified at the genus and species level by the DNA barcoding markers including ITS and *matK*. The amplification and sequencing success rate of *matK* gene was high than that of ITS, so we built phylogenetic tree on the basis of *matK* gene sequences. Our sample, morphologically identified as *Rheum wittrockii*, was also genetically characterized as this species. The novelty of this work is that for the first time DNA barcoding has been used for molecular identification of *Rheum wittrockii* in Uzbekistan. This study will be the foundation for future works aiming to use DNA Barcoding as a plant identification method for *Rheum* species of our flora.

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